

Detection of Accidents in Tunnels Using Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

As urban populations and motor vehicle numbers increase, traffic pollution and congestion have become major concerns. Accidents exacerbate delays, causing injuries, financial losses, and wasted time. The proposed Object Detection and Tracking System (ODTS) aims to address these issues by using advanced technologies to automatically detect and manage irregular events on CCTV in tunnels. The system integrates Faster Regional Convolutional Neural Networks (Faster R-CNN) for object detection and traditional tracking methods. It processes frames to detect objects, assigns unique IDs, and classifies vehicle types using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The tracking algorithm adjusts based on vehicle positions and displays a bird's-eye view on a monitor, also calculating distances between vehicles. ODTS combines YOLO (You Only Look Once) with object tracking to provide real-time information on moving objects. The system is trained to detect objects within specific video frames, identifying coordinates and classifying each object accurately. Key algorithms used include RCNN and YOLO Model.

Keywords: Object Detection and Tracking Technology, (Convolutional Neural NetwoBBox, Regional Convolution Neural Network.

1. INTRODUCTION

Object detection technology identifies the size and position of target objects in images or videos and has applications in self-driving cars, CCTV monitoring, security systems, and cancer detection. Object tracking extends this by identifying and tracking objects over time, relying heavily on the initial object detection performance. This technology has been used for pedestrian and vehicle tracking, accident monitoring, and criminal surveillance. In traffic control, a self-driving car system was developed that uses Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to detect and classify vehicle types.

The system tracks vehicles by adjusting the tracking center point based on their position, displaying a bird's-eye view on a monitor, and calculating distances between vehicles and the driving car. This helps in self-driving car assistance, with localization accuracy within 1.5m vertically and 0.4m horizontally. By leveraging deep learning techniques, various studies contribute to the advancement of Object Detection and Tracking Systems (ODTS), addressing various challenges and improving the accuracy and robustness of vehicle detection and tracking in different environments. Lee et al. [1] highlight the importance of on-road vehicle detection for enhancing driving safety by predicting risks and preventing collisions. Addressing the gap in detecting and localizing partially visible vehicles, this paper presents a novel framework using stereo vision and geometry.

The process begins by creating a v-disparity map from stereo camera images. Object detection is performed on this map, generating vehicle candidates based on expected locations. Deep learning-based verification confirms vehicle detection. For tracking partially visible vehicles, a new algorithm detects the vehicle's grounded edge and uses it as a reference point for Kalman filter tracking. A rectangular box on the bird's-eye view represents the vehicle's longitudinal and lateral position. The proposed system successfully detects and tracks partially visible vehicles. Testing on highway and urban datasets showed a localization performance with a longitudinal error of less than 1.5 meters and a lateral error of 0.4 meters in standard deviation. Cao et al. [2] highlight the emerging research topic of vehicle detection in satellite images, which has various applications but faces challenges due to complex imaging conditions, object variations, and low resolution.

This paper explores the use of deep learning for robust vehicle detection. The proposed framework combines Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DNN) based feature learning with Exemplar-SVMs (E-SVMs) for robust instance classification. DNNs are used to learn discriminative image features, offering significant performance improvements over handcrafted features. E-SVMs enhance classification robustness through instance-specific metric learning. Extensive experiments demonstrate that combining DNN and E-SVM approaches improves detection accuracy and effectiveness, outperforming state-of-the-art methods. Arinaldi et al. [3] present a traffic video analysis system using computer vision techniques to automatically gather vital statistics for policymakers and regulators. These statistics include vehicle counting, type classification, speed estimation, and lane usage monitoring.

The system's core involves detecting and classifying vehicles in traffic videos. Two models are implemented: a MoG + SVM system and Faster RCNN, a deep learning architecture for object detection. Experimental results show that Faster RCNN outperforms MoG in detecting static, overlapping, or nighttime

vehicles. It also surpasses SVM in classifying vehicle types based on appearances. Lee et al. [4] introduce an Object Detection and Tracking System (ODTS) combining Faster R-CNN and conventional tracking algorithms for automatic detection and monitoring of unexpected events on tunnel CCTVs. These events include Wrong-Way Driving (WWD), stopping, a person out of a vehicle, and fire. ODTS processes video frames to generate Bounding Boxes (BBoxes), assigns unique IDs to detected objects by comparing current and previous frames, and tracks moving objects over time.

The deep learning model in ODTS, trained on tunnel event images, achieved Average Precision (AP) values of 0.8479 for cars, 0.7161 for people, and 0.9085 for fires. Zhang et al. [5] review explores the various applications of deep learning in traffic monitoring, discussing techniques and case studies that have successfully implemented object detection and tracking in real-world scenarios. Guoyuan et al. [6] explores the application of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for real-time traffic incident detection. The proposed system uses deep learning models to detect and classify traffic incidents, such as accidents and vehicle breakdowns, from video feeds.

The study demonstrates that CNN-based systems outperform traditional methods in terms of accuracy and speed, making them ideal for real-time traffic monitoring and management. The paper also discusses the challenges and solutions related to implementing these systems in real-world environments. Geetharamani et al. [7] explores various deep learning-based object detection techniques, comparing their effectiveness and applications. It provides a comprehensive overview of methods like Faster R-CNN, YOLO, and SSD (Single Shot Multibox Detector), relevant for developing ODTS. Alexey et al. [8] explored the YOLOv4 builds on the YOLO (You Only Look Once) architecture, focusing on optimizing the trade-off between speed and accuracy in object detection. YOLOv4 introduces several enhancements, such as the use of CSPDarknet53 as the backbone, the PANet path aggregation neck, and the CIoU loss for bounding box regression. This makes YOLOv4 exceptionally fast and accurate, which is critical for applications requiring real-time object detection and tracking, such as traffic monitoring. Ren et al. [9] introduces the Faster R-CNN framework, which integrates Region Proposal Networks (RPN) with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to achieve real-time object detection.

The approach eliminates the need for selective search algorithms by using RPNs to propose regions of interest, which are then classified by the CNN. Faster R-CNN significantly improves both speed and accuracy of object detection, making it suitable for various real-time applications, including traffic monitoring and tunnel surveillance. Zhao et al. [10] provides a comprehensive overview of various deep learning-based object detection methods, including two-stage

detectors like Faster R-CNN, one-stage detectors like YOLO and SSD, and newer models like RetinaNet and Mask R-CNN.

It discusses the strengths and weaknesses of each approach, along with their applications and performance comparisons. Lin et al. [11] introduces the RetinaNet, which uses a novel loss function called Focal Loss to address the issue of class imbalance in object detection. This model combines the efficiency of single-stage detectors like YOLO with the accuracy of two-stage detectors like Faster R-CNN, achieving state-of-the-art performance. From the above literature it was observed that in the deep learning algorithms have the potential to improve the detection of unexpected accidents in tunnels under bad CCTV monitoring conditions. However, there are still challenges to be addressed, such as ensuring the robustness of the algorithms under different lighting and weather conditions, and reducing the computational complexity of the algorithms to enable real-time processing of large amounts of video data. In view of this the present work done on to generate an object detection & tracking system (ODTS) with yolo, that can obtain moving information of target objects with names by combining object tracking algorithm with the deep learning-based object detection process.

2. SYSTEM DESIGN

2.1 Proposed Methodology

In the existing system detects vehicle object and classifies the type of vehicle by Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The vehicle object tracking algorithm tracks the vehicle object by changing the tracking center point according to the position of the recognized vehicle object on the image. Then, the monitor shows a localized image like a bird's viewpoint with the visualized vehicle objects, and the system calculates the distance between the driving car and the visualized vehicle objects. In the proposed system we attempt is made for generate an object detection & tracking system (ODTS) with yolo, that can obtain moving information of target objects with names by combining object tracking algorithm with the deep learning-based object detection process. ODTS receives selected frames of video at specified time interval c and gains sets of coordinates, n BBoxes are detected. BBoxT of objects on the given image frame at the time T , from the trained object detection system. The schematic layout of the system is shown in Fig. 1

Fig. 1 System Architecture

2.2 Data Flow Diagram

- The DFD is also called as bubble chart. It is a simple graphical formalism that can be used to represent a system in terms of input data to the system, various processing carried out on this data, and the output data is generated by this system.
- The data flow diagram (DFD) is one of the most important modeling tools. It is used to model the system components. These components are the system process, the data used by the process, an external entity that interacts with the system and the information flows in the system.
- DFD shows how the information moves through the system and how it is modified by a series of transformations. It is a graphical technique that depicts information flow and the transformations that are applied as data moves from input to output.
- DFD is also known as bubble chart. A DFD may be used to represent a system at any level of abstraction. DFD may be partitioned into levels that represent increasing information flow and functional detail.

The data flow diagram of the system is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Data Flow Diagram

2.3 Activity Diagram

Activity diagrams are graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modeling Language, activity diagrams can be used to describe the business and operational step-by-step workflows of components in a system. An activity diagram shows the overall flow of control.

Fig. 3 Activity Diagram

3. TESTING

3.1 Need for Testing

The purpose of testing is to discover errors. Testing is the process of trying to discover every conceivable fault or weakness in a work product. It provides a way to check the functionality of components, sub-assemblies, assemblies and/or a finished product. It is the process of exercising software with the intent of ensuring that the Software system meets its requirements and user expectations and does not fail in an unacceptable manner. There are various types of test. Each test type addresses a specific testing requirement. The following test cases mentioned in Table.1 have passed successfully and it was observed no defects.

Table 1 Passed System Test Cases :

Test Case	ExceptedResult	Result
Loading Yolo	Yolo names and yolo configuration loaded from disk	Pass
Load CCTV video file disk	Loading CCTV video through CV2	Pass
Split video into images	Splitting video into images and stored in disk	Pass
Applying object detecting algorithm with CNN	For each image object detection algorithm applied	Pass
Box the detected object	Round the vehicle object with names	Pass
Get accident images	For moving vehicles accident Happened name with crash images	Pass
Detect image wrong side or not	Detecting the images wrong sided driving of Vehicles	Pass

Identifying the vehicles lines in the road	Lines identified then only wrong driving is Detected	Pass
Fire Detected	User should upload a video which contains fires	Pass
All images combine the a video file	Video detected and played in CV2 frames	Pass

4. RESULTS

```

C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe - python cch_video.py --input_line\cch\mp4 --yolo\yolo-coco
Box[4]: 648 137 14 12 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.8793113827705383
Box[1]: 586 111 20 13 Labels[1]: car classIDs[1]: 2 AveragePrecision[1]: 0.858701765537262
Box[0]: 692 541 132 99 Labels[0]: car classIDs[0]: 2 AveragePrecision[0]: 0.8516795831680298
Box[5]: 612 177 23 18 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.8048548102378845
Box[2]: 666 111 14 11 Labels[2]: car classIDs[2]: 2 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.7368763089179993
Box[3]: 518 136 19 18 Labels[3]: car classIDs[3]: 2 AveragePrecision[3]: 0.706872284412384
Complete time for algorithm 4.234575986062183
Frame No: 3
Box[5]: 648 137 14 12 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.8508764505386353
Box[2]: 586 111 20 13 Labels[2]: car classIDs[2]: 2 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.8288004292678833
Box[6]: 612 177 24 18 Labels[6]: car classIDs[6]: 2 AveragePrecision[6]: 0.8061835169792175
Box[4]: 518 136 19 18 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.7166885137557983
Box[1]: 718 561 126 102 Labels[1]: car classIDs[1]: 2 AveragePrecision[1]: 0.7150619029998779
Box[3]: 667 111 13 11 Labels[3]: car classIDs[3]: 2 AveragePrecision[3]: 0.6504494547843933
Complete time for algorithm 4.794259548187256
Frame No: 4
Box[6]: 610 174 23 17 Labels[6]: car classIDs[6]: 2 AveragePrecision[6]: 0.8361181020736694
Box[5]: 641 136 12 11 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.7916293144226074
Box[1]: 588 115 13 10 Labels[1]: car classIDs[1]: 2 AveragePrecision[1]: 0.6933873891830444
Box[3]: 668 110 12 11 Labels[3]: car classIDs[3]: 2 AveragePrecision[3]: 0.6624507308006287
Box[0]: 710 571 139 116 Labels[0]: car classIDs[0]: 2 AveragePrecision[0]: 0.6585932807922263
Box[2]: 584 111 22 14 Labels[2]: car classIDs[2]: 2 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.6124014258384705
Box[4]: 519 136 17 20 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.5921458257301331
Complete time for algorithm 4.602364778518677
Frame No: 5
Box[0]: 741 590 137 120 Labels[0]: car classIDs[0]: 2 AveragePrecision[0]: 0.8740738034248352
Box[5]: 641 135 13 12 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.8562538623809014
Box[6]: 609 173 24 17 Labels[6]: car classIDs[6]: 2 AveragePrecision[6]: 0.8287186826573181
Box[1]: 579 114 13 11 Labels[1]: car classIDs[1]: 2 AveragePrecision[1]: 0.7563843832778931
Box[3]: 667 110 13 11 Labels[3]: car classIDs[3]: 2 AveragePrecision[3]: 0.6890048384666443
Box[2]: 583 110 24 15 Labels[2]: car classIDs[2]: 2 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.5966717004776001
Box[7]: 507 182 34 45 Labels[7]: truck classIDs[7]: 7 AveragePrecision[7]: 0.5317394137382507
Box[4]: 518 136 17 22 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.5133826520774841
Complete time for algorithm 4.39048518371582
Frame No: 6
Box[1]: 579 114 13 11 Labels[1]: car classIDs[1]: 2 AveragePrecision[1]: 0.8311843872070312
Box[4]: 646 135 13 11 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.8223688006401062
Box[5]: 610 172 23 18 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.7748073935508728
Box[0]: 750 598 141 115 Labels[0]: car classIDs[0]: 2 AveragePrecision[0]: 0.7464068531998051
Box[2]: 669 110 12 11 Labels[2]: car classIDs[2]: 2 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.6212339997291565
Box[3]: 517 136 18 22 Labels[3]: car classIDs[3]: 2 AveragePrecision[3]: 0.5606511831203569
Complete time for algorithm 4.78289058242796
Frame No: 7
    
```

Fig. 4 Starting each frames

Fig. 5 Output frames

Fig. 6 Output detection

```
C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe - python cch_video.py --input test.mp4 --yolo yolo-coco
Box[15]: 614 383 64 60 Labels[15]: car classIDs[15]: 2 AveragePrecision[15]: 0.9708886742591858
Box[14]: 384 321 73 56 Labels[14]: car classIDs[14]: 2 AveragePrecision[14]: 0.963583767414093
Box[11]: 639 217 30 20 Labels[11]: car classIDs[11]: 2 AveragePrecision[11]: 0.9084933400154114
Box[2]: 1005 415 132 118 Labels[2]: truck classIDs[2]: 7 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.8711925745010376
Box[10]: 520 212 33 27 Labels[10]: car classIDs[10]: 2 AveragePrecision[10]: 0.804610239402771
Box[8]: 604 166 29 21 Labels[8]: car classIDs[8]: 2 AveragePrecision[8]: 0.8000059127807617
Box[7]: 639 149 20 18 Labels[7]: car classIDs[7]: 2 AveragePrecision[7]: 0.76325923204422
Box[6]: 637 137 22 18 Labels[6]: car classIDs[6]: 2 AveragePrecision[6]: 0.7327922582626343
Box[5]: 547 135 17 13 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.7002130091491699
Box[4]: 586 101 19 11 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.5455284118652344
Box[9]: 448 216 32 26 Labels[9]: car classIDs[9]: 2 AveragePrecision[9]: 0.5142262570010559
Complete time for algorithm 4.112649440765381
Frame No: 46
Box[3]: 487 495 111 98 Labels[3]: car classIDs[3]: 2 AveragePrecision[3]: 0.9819610714912415
Box[13]: 593 312 49 53 Labels[13]: car classIDs[13]: 2 AveragePrecision[13]: 0.970967010074884
Box[12]: 450 313 193 52 Labels[12]: car classIDs[12]: 2 AveragePrecision[12]: 0.9677761793136597
Box[14]: 385 320 78 58 Labels[14]: car classIDs[14]: 2 AveragePrecision[14]: 0.9627906684006669
Box[15]: 609 306 74 64 Labels[15]: car classIDs[15]: 2 AveragePrecision[15]: 0.9615304936332703
Box[2]: 996 404 133 116 Labels[2]: truck classIDs[2]: 7 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.9123777473154236
Box[11]: 638 213 30 23 Labels[11]: car classIDs[11]: 2 AveragePrecision[11]: 0.8713926676809038
Box[10]: 520 210 36 31 Labels[10]: car classIDs[10]: 2 AveragePrecision[10]: 0.81633455123352
Box[5]: 544 135 19 14 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.800649252418518
Box[8]: 605 165 28 19 Labels[8]: car classIDs[8]: 2 AveragePrecision[8]: 0.7080472445487976
Box[7]: 639 149 19 17 Labels[7]: car classIDs[7]: 2 AveragePrecision[7]: 0.7330524325370789
Box[6]: 638 134 22 20 Labels[6]: car classIDs[6]: 2 AveragePrecision[6]: 0.674657940864563
Box[9]: 445 216 35 26 Labels[9]: car classIDs[9]: 2 AveragePrecision[9]: 0.6428461074829102
Box[4]: 584 101 19 11 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.5080229640067019
Complete time for algorithm 4.166612148284912
Frame No: 47
[INFO] cleaning up...
[Msg] Accidents frames analysed
[INFO] Wrong Driving Analysis Started
extracting frames from image
Reading and resizing the first image
Shape of First Image: (200, 400)
Minimum Intensity: 0
Maximum Intensity: 255
```

Fig. 7 Preprocess of system

```
C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe - python cch_video.py --input test.mp4 --yolo yolo-coco
Box[15]: 614 383 64 60 Labels[15]: car classIDs[15]: 2 AveragePrecision[15]: 0.9708886742591858
Box[14]: 384 321 73 56 Labels[14]: car classIDs[14]: 2 AveragePrecision[14]: 0.963583767414093
Box[11]: 639 217 30 20 Labels[11]: car classIDs[11]: 2 AveragePrecision[11]: 0.9084933400154114
Box[2]: 1005 415 132 118 Labels[2]: truck classIDs[2]: 7 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.8711925745010376
Box[10]: 520 212 33 27 Labels[10]: car classIDs[10]: 2 AveragePrecision[10]: 0.804610239402771
Box[8]: 604 166 29 21 Labels[8]: car classIDs[8]: 2 AveragePrecision[8]: 0.8000059127807617
Box[7]: 639 149 20 18 Labels[7]: car classIDs[7]: 2 AveragePrecision[7]: 0.76325923204422
Box[6]: 637 137 22 18 Labels[6]: car classIDs[6]: 2 AveragePrecision[6]: 0.7327922582626343
Box[5]: 547 135 17 13 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.7002130091491699
Box[4]: 586 101 19 11 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.5455284118652344
Box[9]: 448 216 32 26 Labels[9]: car classIDs[9]: 2 AveragePrecision[9]: 0.5142262570010559
Complete time for algorithm 4.112649440765381
Frame No: 46
Box[3]: 487 495 111 98 Labels[3]: car classIDs[3]: 2 AveragePrecision[3]: 0.9819610714912415
Box[13]: 593 312 49 53 Labels[13]: car classIDs[13]: 2 AveragePrecision[13]: 0.970967010074884
Box[12]: 450 313 193 52 Labels[12]: car classIDs[12]: 2 AveragePrecision[12]: 0.9677761793136597
Box[14]: 385 320 78 58 Labels[14]: car classIDs[14]: 2 AveragePrecision[14]: 0.9627906684006669
Box[15]: 609 306 74 64 Labels[15]: car classIDs[15]: 2 AveragePrecision[15]: 0.9615304936332703
Box[2]: 996 404 133 116 Labels[2]: truck classIDs[2]: 7 AveragePrecision[2]: 0.9123777473154236
Box[11]: 638 213 30 23 Labels[11]: car classIDs[11]: 2 AveragePrecision[11]: 0.8713926676809038
Box[10]: 520 210 36 31 Labels[10]: car classIDs[10]: 2 AveragePrecision[10]: 0.81633455123352
Box[5]: 544 135 19 14 Labels[5]: car classIDs[5]: 2 AveragePrecision[5]: 0.800649252418518
Box[8]: 605 165 28 19 Labels[8]: car classIDs[8]: 2 AveragePrecision[8]: 0.7080472445487976
Box[7]: 639 149 19 17 Labels[7]: car classIDs[7]: 2 AveragePrecision[7]: 0.7330524325370789
Box[6]: 638 134 22 20 Labels[6]: car classIDs[6]: 2 AveragePrecision[6]: 0.674657940864563
Box[9]: 445 216 35 26 Labels[9]: car classIDs[9]: 2 AveragePrecision[9]: 0.6428461074829102
Box[4]: 584 101 19 11 Labels[4]: car classIDs[4]: 2 AveragePrecision[4]: 0.5080229640067019
Complete time for algorithm 4.166612148284912
Frame No: 47
[INFO] cleaning up...
[Msg] Accidents frames analysed
[INFO] Wrong Driving Analysis Started
extracting frames from image
Reading and resizing the first image
Shape of First Image: (200, 400)
Minimum Intensity: 0
Maximum Intensity: 255
```

Fig. 8 Comparison of first image

Fig. 9 Comparison of second image

Fig. 10 Smooth detection

Fig. 11 Space count

Fig. 12 Making video

Fig. 13 Crash detected

Fig. 14 Identifying of the driving line

Fig. 15 Image with left mask

Fig. 16 Average Gradient image

Fig. 17 UV orientation

Fig. 18 Vehicle direction detection

Overall, testing is a critical part of the implementation of the system as it helps to ensure that it can accurately and reliably detect incidents under challenging monitoring conditions in tunnels. The testing process involves evaluating the model, fine-tuning it, integrating it with the CCTV system, and testing it with real-world scenarios to ensure that it meets the requirements of the tunnel operators and improves the safety and efficiency of tunnel traffic management as shown in Fig 4-18.

5. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a novel Object Detection and Tracking System (ODTS) that integrates a deep learning-based object detection network with an object tracking algorithm. The system demonstrates that dynamic information for a specific object class can be effectively obtained and utilized for real-time applications. While object detection performance is crucial for the effectiveness of the ODTS, it is worth noting that the Simple Online and Realtime Tracking (SORT) algorithm used in this system relies solely on bounding box (BBox) information without incorporating image data. Therefore, continuous object detection may be less critical unless the object tracking algorithm's performance is highly dependent on object recognition accuracy.

A Tunnel CCTV Accident Detection System based on the proposed ODTS was developed and evaluated. Experiments involved training and assessing the deep learning object detection network and testing the overall system's capability to detect accidents. The system includes a Context-Aware Dynamic Adapter (CADA) that analyzes dynamic information of car objects for improved accuracy.

The experimental results showed that the system could detect accidents within 10 seconds when presented with images of each accident scenario. Deep learning techniques successfully ensured reliable performance for detecting car objects, though person detection exhibited relatively lower performance. Additionally, the detection of fire was prone to false positives in untrained videos due to the insufficient number of fire images used for training. However, incorporating a countermeasure for non-fire objects during training can help mitigate the occurrence of false detections.

Overall, the proposed ODTS effectively combines deep learning-based detection with dynamic tracking to provide a robust solution for accident detection in tunnel environments, offering promising results and identifying areas for further improvement.

5.1 Future Recommendations

The fire object detection performance of the deep learning object detection network should be improved by securing the Fire image later. Although the ODTS can be applied as an example of a Tunnel CCTV Accident Detection System, it is also used to fields that need to monitor the dynamic movement of a specific object such as vehicle speed estimation or illegal parking monitoring will be possible. To increase the reliability of the system, it is necessary to secure various images and to secure Fire and Person objects. Besides, through the application and continuous monitoring of the tunnel management site, the reliability of the system could be improved.

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